

Synthesis of Possible Antifertility Compounds. Synthesis of *Bis* and *Di* Derivatives of Coumarins

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Manuscript received 16 February 1977, accepted 4 July 1977

Several new *bis* and *di* (7 or 4-coumarinyloxy) alkanes have been prepared as possible antifertility agents. The structure has been ascertained by their elemental analysis and the mass spectra of one representative *bis*-coumarin.

MAJORITY of neutral coumarins show appreciable estrogenic activity which is due to the oxygen atom in heterocyclic ring and a *p*-OH group in the 2-aryl substituent. Recently Lednicer et al² prepared a number of 3, 4 diaryl coumarins, sterically related to 1, 2-diarylindene and showed that some of them possess antifertility activity presumably due to their estrogenic activity and they also exhibited antiimplantation activity in rats.

Marked antifertility activity has been observed in compounds incorporating a triarylethylene or ethane pattern and also in 3, 4-diphenyl, 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-napthalene when the alkoxy group³⁻⁶ was introduced in the nucleus of former and halogen⁷⁻⁹ substituent is incorporated in the phenyl rings of the latter. Recently some alkoxy and halogen substituted 3,4-diaryl-coumarins with a possible antifertility interest were also synthesised by Tiwari and Kumar¹⁰.

In view of these observations the present authors prepared several additional analogues of neutral *bis* (I) and *dicoumarins* (II) with methyl, ethyl, acetyl and chloro substituents in the rings.

7-Hydroxycoumarins were prepared by adopting the procedure of Pechman¹¹. 7-hydroxy, 4-methyl and 6-substituted coumarins were obtained by using the method of Chakravarti and Ghosh¹² and 4-hydroxy coumarin was synthesised by using the procedure of J. Boyd and A. Robertson¹³. Thus in all eleven new compounds were synthesised. The analytical data are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Bioassay

Anti-implantation activity: The *in vivo* anti-implantation activity of all the eleven compounds was studied on adult albino proven female and male rats.

In this preliminary screening female rats were treated with the drug at a dose of 20 mg/Kg. Four

such rats, constituted a group and a female : male ratio of 4 : 1 was maintained. The compounds, under test, were suspended in a mixture of gum acacia and distilled water. The suspension was fed orally from day 1 to 5 post-coitum. The day in which the sperms were seen in the vaginal smears was taken as the day 1 of the pregnancy. The animals were laprotomized on the 10th day of the pregnancy and the number of implantations in each case was noted. However, none of the compounds was found active at this dose.

Anti-estrogenic activity of these compounds is at present in progress and the results will be published later.

Experimental

1. *Bis-(7 or 4-coumarinyloxy) alkanes*: An appropriate hydroxycoumarin (.025 mole) and a dibromoalkane (.01 mole) were refluxed together in dry acetone (80 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (8 g.) for 36 hours till a negative ferric chloride test was observed. The reaction mixture was filtered while hot and the resultant precipitate washed first with 10% NaOH solution and then with water. The solid thus obtained was recrystallised from D. M. F.-water mixture.

2. *Di-(7 or 4-coumarinyloxy) alkanes*: A mixture of two different coumarins (1 : 1) and dibromo alkane (0.1 mole) were refluxed in dry acetone and anhydrous potassium carbonate (0.2 mole) for 36 hours and the resultant product was isolated as in the previous case.

Mass Spectrum: As the compounds were insoluble in solvents generally used in N. M. R. spectroscopy and comparable I.R. data are not available, mass spectra of one of the *bis*-coumarins, i.e. compound No. 4 of Table I was determined. The mass spectra confirms the mol. weight of the *bis*-coumarin (M^+ 392).

TABLE I

Sl. No.	R	R'	R''	N	m. p°. °C	Mol. formula	Calculated		Found	
							C%	H%	C%	H%
<i>Series a</i>										
1	-H	-H	-H	2	250	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₆	68.56	4.00	68.02	3.99
2	-CH ₃	-H	-H	2	227	C ₉ H ₁₈ O ₆	69.84	4.76	69.94	4.71
3	-H	-H	-H	3	160	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₆	69.23	4.12	68.99	4.25
4	-H	-H	-H	3	189	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₆	70.40	5.10	70.90	5.36
5	-H	-Cl	-H	3	120	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₆ Cl ₂	59.86	4.12	59.41	4.32
6	-H	-H	-COCH	3	212	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ O ₈	68.03	4.91	67.89	4.58
<i>Series b</i>										
7	-	-	-	3	181	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₆	69.23	4.39	69.51	4.62

TABLE 2

Sl. No.	R	R	n	m. p°. °C	Mol. formula	Calculated		Found		
						C%	H%	C%	H%	
<i>Series c</i>										
1	-CH ₃ , -H	-H	3	162	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₆	69.84	4.76	69.25	4.28	
2	-CH ₃ , -CH ₃	-C ₂ H ₅ , -H	3	150	C ₂₅ H ₂₄ O ₆	71.19	5.71	71.38	5.99	
<i>Series d</i>										
3	-CH ₃	-H	3	158	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ O ₆	69.84	4.76	69.53	4.59	
4	-H	-H	2	225	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₆	68.33	4.00	68.57	3.91	

* All melting points are uncorrected and were taken in open capillary tubes.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Head of the Department of Chemistry for providing the necessary research facilities and C.D.R.I., Lucknow for the bioassay work and elemental analysis. One of them (S.A.) is thankful to the C.S.I.R., for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

References

1. Gley et. al., *compt. rend. Soc. biol.*, 1945, 139, 1055, *Bull. Soc., Chim.*, 1946, 271.
2. D. LEDNICER, J. C. BABCOCK, P. F. MARLATT, S. C. LYSTER and G.W. Duncan, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1965, 8, 52.
3. D. LEDNICER, S. C. LYSTER and G. W. DUNCAN, *J Med. Chem.*, 1965, 8, 725.
4. R S. SHELTON, et al.; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 5491.
5. E. C. DODDS, et al. ; *Proc. Roy. Soc., (London)*, 1939, B127, 140.
6. C. R. THOMPSON and H. W. WERNER, *Proc. Soc. Expt. Biol. Med.* : 1951, 77, 494.
7. D. LEDNICER, S. C. LYSTER, B. D ASPERGEN and G. W. DUNCAN, *Proc. Soc. Expt. Biol. Med.* ; 1966, 9, 172.
8. R. W. J. CARNEY, W. L. BENCZE, J. WOJTKUNSKI, A. A. RENZI, L. DORFMAN and G. DESTEVES ; *Proc. Soc. Expt. Biol. Med.*, 1966, 9, 516.
9. W. L. BENCZE, et al., *J. Med. Chem.*, 1967, 10, 138.
10. S. S. TIWARI and SUBODH KUMAR, *Ind. J. Appl. Chem.* 1971, 2, 34.
11. PECHMANN, *Ber*, 1884, 17, 929.
12. CHAKRAVARTI and GHOSH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 623.
13. J. BOYD and A. ROBERTSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 174.